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INFLUENCE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING ON MOTIVATION OF FIRST-YEAR STUDENTS IN ENERGY ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

The way energy is generated and provided is changing rapidly. Many engineers are required to overcome these new challenges. High drop-out rates, especially in engineering study courses, are therefore a serious problem. Hence, new concepts are needed to reduce them.

Factors like study motivation and interest in subjects have a proven high influence on the drop-out rates [1]. Additionally a high degree of identification with the subject and a good professional perspective support the probability of graduation [1], while the method of project-based learning has shown positive effects on the motivation to study [2].

In this study, it will be investigated how project-based learning affects the motivation to study and the identification with the subject of energy engineering students in their first and successive semesters. In an experimental control group design, a new concept will be developed, which shall not only increase motivation but act as a connecting link of the study course by giving an overview of the interrelationships between the

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subjects and accompanying the students as a guiding thread for their studies. While the experimental group will attend a new practical concept with project-based tasks, the control group will deal with topics similar to those of the experimental group, but in a more theoretical context. The motivation and the identification with the subject will be measured in a pre-post-design by questionnaires. A follow-up at the end of the second semester will investigate the medium-term development of the examined variables.

1 INTRODUCTION

The energy demand of mankind is enormous. Many innovative concepts and developments are needed to ensure a reliable energy supply, especially in times of dwindling fossil fuel reserves. To master these challenges, a large number of well-trained engineers is necessary.

However, particularly in the engineering sector, high drop-out rates have been recorded in Germany in the recent years [1]. For the German graduating cohort of 2012, the drop-out rate in engineering at universities of applied sciences was 31 %, which is well above the overall average of 23 % [1]. In accordance with [3], the drop-out rate for engineering students even shows a further increase in the following years.

Dropout can be understood as a process that is driven by different internal and external factors and conditions. One of the main reasons for dropping out is a lack of study motivation. Students no longer identify closely with their chosen subject or career prospects. [1]

According to [3], for 64 % of dropped out engineering students at German universities of applied sciences, study motivation plays a significant or major role in their drop-out process. Furthermore, the dropout due to lack of study motivation can be observed as one of the earliest. 53 % of students, who stated the missing study motivation as a main reason for dropping out, left the higher education institution in the first two semesters. [3]

A method that has proven to show positive effects on students' motivation for their studies is project-based learning [2]. It is based on authentic problems, supported by a driving question [4], which should place the students in realistic and contextualized problem-solving environments [5]. Students can work moreover quite autonomously [4], which gives them room for developing own approaches and choices and engages them in investigation [5]. Furthermore, solving authentic problems increases their interest in the subject [5]. Project-based learning also links among subject matter disciplines and gives therefore a wider view of subject matter [5].

2 AIM OF THE STUDY AND RESEARCH QUESTION

One approach to reduce drop-out rates in the engineering sector can thus be to increase the students' motivation to study. It becomes equally clear that this should happen as early as possible. This study will investigate, how project-based learning tasks affect the motivation to study and the identification with the subject of energy engineering students in their first and successive semesters. It is carried out at a German university of applied sciences.

3 METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

To promote the students' motivation to study, a new first semester module is designed. It consists of two components, a lecture with integrated exercise and a workshop (Fig. 1). Each component pursues different aims. The lecture gives an overview of the field and creates context in relation to historical developments and future challenges. This conveys in particular the relevance of the topic and creates a subject-specific orientation in the study course. In the workshop, the students investigate technical and scientific interrelationships. This also includes the development of competencies. By gaining the opportunity to get to know the various facilities at the university and the research areas of their faculty, students will feel integrated into academic life at the university from the very beginning. The interaction of both components then promotes the two main objectives of the module concept, increasing the students' motivation to study as well as their identification with the subject and the university.

Fig. 1. Structural design of the new module with specification of component objectives

The project-based learning is integrated into the workshop as the independent variable. Its effects are measured in a pre-post-design (Fig. 2). Therefore, a set of dependent variables is defined (Fig. 2). The dependent variables will be measured by questionnaires. With a follow-up at the end of the second semester, the medium-term development of the effects will be investigated.

Fig. 2. Design of the measurement

To ensure that the measured effects are due to the independent variable, an experimental control group design is chosen for the intervention (Fig. 3).

All students participate in the lecture with integrated exercise. In the Workshop, the experimental group as well as the control group investigate concepts of modern and renewable energy systems. Both groups will deal with the same topics over the same time in order to be equally prepared for the exam at the end of the semester.

The difference will be that the experimental group works mainly practical in project-based tasks and will be accompanied throughout the semester by a driving question that links the topics to be worked on with an authentic problem. Here, the students will develop a concept for the integration of renewable energy systems in a residential building that is to be renovated. The participants of the control group will work more theoretically by only studying literature about energy systems, but without the connecting element of the driving question and other typical project-based learning elements.

Fig. 3. Structure of the experimental control group design

4 PERSPECTIVE

Due to an expected limited number of participants in winter semester 2020/2021, the planned pilot study will be postponed to winter semester 2021/2022. The pilot study will evaluate the design and the test instruments, that will be selected in a next step.

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